

Antibody Characterization Report for PATL2 (UniProt ID: C9JE40) YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

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Target:

Recommended protein name: Protein PAT1 homolog 2

Protein name used in this report: PATL2

Alternative protein name: PAT1-like protein 2, Protein PAT1 homolog a

Gene name: *PATL2*

Uniprot: C9JE40

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. In this study, we characterized six PATL2 commercial antibodies for western blot and immunoprecipitation. We identified well-performing antibodies and encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibody for their specific needs. A human *PATL2* construct in the pcDNA3.1(+) vector (cloned at GenScript) was used to overexpress the protein.

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
ATCC	CRL-3216	CVCL_0063	HEK 293T	WT

Table 2: Summary of the PATL2 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Bioss Antibodies	bs-19898R	BA11302340	n/a	polyclonal		rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Novus Biologicals (Bio-Techne)	NBP3-09553	QC38052	AB_3094819	polyclonal		rabbit	0.50	Wb
St Jhons lab	STJ195099	9RC140RC14	n/a	polyclonal		rabbit	1.00	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	AB5587	411606	n/a	polyclonal		rabbit	0.50	n/a
Thermo Fisher Scientific	AB5588	411606	n/a	polyclonal		rabbit	0.50	n/a
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-48187	WG333947	AB_2633645	polyclonal		rabbit	0.43	Wb, IF

Wb=western blot, IF=immunofluorescence, n/a=not available

Note: AB5587 and AB5588 are custom-made antibodies, and a newer version of this report will be uploaded upon their commercial availability.

Materials and methods

Cell culture

HEK 293T cells (Table 1) were cultured in DMEM high glucose (GE Healthcare cat. number SH30081.01) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 2 mM L-glutamine (Wisent cat. number 609-065, 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201). To transiently express the protein, cells were seeded in 150 mm dishes to 60% confluence then transfected with 10 µg of the human *PATL2* pcDNA3.1(+) plasmid using the Calcium Phosphate method. Cells were lysed 48 hrs after transfection.

Antibodies

All the *PATL2* antibodies tested are listed in Table 2. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit is from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 65-6120). Peroxidase-conjugated Protein A is from Cell Signaling Technology, cat. number 12291.

Antibody screening by western blot

Western blots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [2]. HEK 293T WT (Table 1) and transiently expressing *PATL2* were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer from Bio-Rad (cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST.

Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Immunoprecipitation was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [2]. Antibody-beads conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30µl of Dynabeads protein A- (rabbit antibodies) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 10002D). Tubes were rocked for ~1 hr at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

HEK 293T WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2.0 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 hr at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP lysis buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels. Protein A:HRP (Cell Signaling Technology, cat. number 12291) was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 0.5 µg/ml.

Figure 1: PATL2 antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: PATL2 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 1: PATL2 antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates from HEK 293T WT (-) and transiently expressing human *PATL2* (+) were prepared, and 40 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated PATL2 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. All antibodies were used at 1 µg/ml. Predicted band size: 61.4 kDa.

Figure 2: PATL2 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

Lysates from HEK 293T transiently expressing human *PATL2* were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 2.0 µg of the indicated PATL2 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the indicated PATL2 antibody. For western blot, AB5587 was used at 1 µg/ml. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitated; Wb=western blot.

References

1. Laflamme, C., et al., *Opinion: Independent third-party entities as a model for validation of commercial antibodies*. N Biotechnol, 2021. **65**: p. 1-8 DOI: 10.1016/j.nbt.2021.07.001.
2. Ayoubi, R., et al., *A consensus platform for antibody characterization*. 2024 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1>.